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EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF REMOTE LEARNING ON ENGINEERING REPORT WRITING SKILLS USING ACADEMIC ASSESSMENT AND AUTOMATIC NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

Written communication skills are considered an important yet underdeveloped skill in student engineers compared to those studying humanities. Motivated to evaluate existing techniques to automatically measure writing skills and discover their relationship to the academic grades awarded by engineering educators, this paper reports an analysis of an individual engineering research report writing exercise that all students complete after one semester in their first year engineering degree programmes. The exercise has been taken by 1360 students from 2017 to 2020. The performance is compared across the four year-cohorts via academic assessment and automatic readability assessment. While the first three-year results are from students who are taught on campus, the last cohort is taught exclusively online with no opportunities for students to meet in person due to the restrictions under the COVID-19 pandemic. To evaluate whether there is any marked change in the qualities of student report writing skills very early in their university studies due to the lack of cohort interaction and shared physical experience, eight classic readability assessment measures are calculated for each report and compared with the grade awarded for the report. We find that two classic readability measures - Coleman Liau and Dale Chall - have a higher correlation with the academic assessment and complement each other due to low correlation with each other. We combine them and further improve the correlation with the academic grade. The work highlights the potential of using readability assessment in engineering education as a learning support tool and to improve assessment reliability.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Is it possible to automatically assess the readability of an engineering student's technical writing, and how would this automatic readability assessment correlate with an academically-assessed grade, which would take into account technical quality and context? Moreover, has the covid-19 pandemic affected, on average, students' report writing compared with recent years? In this study we answer these questions by examining research reports from four successive first-year general engineering cohorts and consider different methods for automatically assessing the reports' readability.

1.1 Report Writing Skills

Written communication skills are an important skill for engineering students [1]. They are shown to influence career choice and success [2]. However, it is still a widely-held view that modern engineering curricula does not place significant emphasis upon them [3]. By the virtue of the type of secondary school focus of their studies in numerical and scientific subjects in order to enter engineering higher education in the United Kingdom, students do not develop writing skills explicitly further than English language secondary school level, with which they communicate their ideas and research in the scientific subjects.

In the particular report writing exercise considered in this paper, the instructor reminds students that writing skills are important because they are likely to produce many reports as engineers. A report is "a statement of the results of an investigation or of any matter on which definite information is required". They are introduced to an engineering report as having a very formal structure, that leads the reader through the information efficiently and that makes it easy for non-experts to glean information. They are expected to structure the report under the headings of title page, acknowledgements, content, abstract or executive summary, the main body, references and appendices.

1.2 Impact of Covid 19

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic is likely to be studied for many years to come. In higher education, there was an almost immediate move to online teaching and assessment because students could not attend in person with many residing in different countries and in different time zones. The lack of social interaction between students online, particularly any cohort that was coming together for the first time as in the case of first year undergraduates, raised additional challenges to cohorts that had come together prior to the pandemic and in which friendships and face-to-face group work had taken place which formed and deepened acquaintances. The lack of these interactions between students and their instructors could have an impact on learning and skills development.

In this paper, the authors choose to focus on report writing skills for first year undergraduate students to assess whether online instruction versus in-person instruction and tutoring could have impacted on the report writing skills of different cohorts. To achieve this, reports produced under the same instructions but covering

four cohorts are assessed and compared. Only the last of the cohorts are taught online. The readability of the reports, assessed automatically due to the sheer volume (1360) is investigated to identify any possible trends arising from the different type of instruction and a lack of personal interaction between students.

1.3 Automatic Readability Assessment

The quest to find a reliable automatic measure of text comprehension is an active research area that spans almost a century [4]. Applications in the education domain include assessing reading age level, automated essay scoring, and providing student feedback [5]. Readability Assessment (RA) involves parsing text to extract quantitative measures, from which a score is calculated. Parameters used to compute the score are determined empirically to match a gold standard recorded in a text corpus. This standard is typically a score derived from human judgement and/or demographic information, such as age.

Hundreds of RA methods exist. In a recent review of the field [6], methods were described as classical formulas that compute a score based on frequency and length of text units such as words and sentences, and methods that use more advanced linguistic and semantic features from Natural Language Processing (NLP). These advanced features are combined with statistical and machine learning methods to determine the best feature set.

Despite the promise of recent advances, classical formulas persist due to their ease of comprehension and application. In the Engineering domain, recent applications of classical formulas include assessing design standards [7] and distinguishing academic abstracts [8].

1.4 Structure

This paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 outlines the data, methodology for analysing the correlation between report readability and grade, and the three experiments performed. Section 3 presents our results and findings, including follow-on work to combine automatic readability measures to improve correlation with academic assessment. Section 4 finishes with discussion and future work.

2 METHOD

2.1 Text Corpus

Reports from the same assignment taken by different students over 4 years from 2017-2020 are collected together with the grade awarded, which is an academic assessment of the quality of the report taking into account the technical quality and knowledge understanding of the topic, rather than notions of general readability. Text from each report is extracted and frontmatter and backmatter removed. In total 1360 reports are processed. Cohort numbers are comparable between years, ranging between 315 and 398. The mean word count for reports is 1684 with a standard deviation of 437. The normalised mean grade is 0.69 with a standard deviation of 0.11. There is no significant difference between grades awarded each year, as shown in the frequency histogram in fig. 1.

Figure 1 Frequency histogram comparing grade distribution normalised to 1 across years, overlayed with a normal distribution curve fit for each year. There is no significant difference between distributions.

Classic Readability Assessment (RA) measures are computed for each report. These methods are summarised in Table 1. All RA methods typically apply an estimated linear function to produce a readability score, where the inputs are a subset of counts of sentence, word, syllable and letter. In some algorithms, word counts are further distinguished by taking into account word complexity using either grammatical analysis or usage estimates.

Table 1 RA method comparison of input features (counts)

RA method(year introduced)	Sentence	Word	Letter	syllables	complexity
Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level (1975)	x	x		x	
Flesch Reading Ease (1948)	x	x		x	
Dale Chall Readability (1995)	x				x
Automated Readability Index (1967)	x	x	x		
Coleman Liau Index (1975)	x		x		
Gunning Fog (1952)	x	x			x
SPACHE (1952)	x	x		x	
Linsear Write (1966)	x				x

2.2 Experiments

Three experiments are conducted with the RA measures extracted from the reports:

Experiment 1: Correlation between RA measures and grade. The linear and monotonic relationship between measures and grade for each report is explored by calculating the Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients respectively.

Experiment 2: Correlation between RA measures. These are compared to identify those which can be considered complementary or redundant. The relationship is similarly explored with the Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients.

Experiment 3: An optimum RA measure is proposed to predict grade. A selected number of measures are combined to discover a readability measure which has a higher correlation with academic assessment than others.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Experiment 1: Correlation between RA measures and grade

Correlation of RA measures with academic assessment (Table 2) reveals that all measures are weakly correlated with grade. CL has the highest correlation when considering the linear case, while DC has the highest correlation when considering the monotonic case. Scatterplotting these two methods to visualise these relationships with grade (Fig. 2) illustrates this.

Table 2 Correlation of readability measures with grade including ours (see section 3.2)

Method	Pearson (linear)	Spearman (monotonic)
Flesch-Kincaid	-0.012	-0.077
Flesch Reading Ease	0.020	0.065
Dale Chall Readability	0.084	<u>0.281</u>
Automated Readability Index	-0.012	-0.091
Coleman Liau Index	<u>-0.126</u>	-0.062
Gunning Fog	-0.012	-0.074
SPACHE	0.007	0.084
Linsear Write	-0.010	-0.057
Ours	-0.154	0.320

Fig. 2 CL weak linear relationship (left) DC weak monotonic relationship (right)

3.2 Experiment 2: Correlation between RA measures

Fig. 3 shows the linear and monotonic correlations respectively between readability methods for all text ($n=1360$) in heat-map form. Most methods have high correlations (either positive or negative) with the exception of Coleman Liau (CL) which does not correlate with any other measure. This suggests that CL may be useful in combination with other measures, and that the other methods are relatively interchangeable. For the monotonic (ordinal rank) relationship, the comparison also reveals that CL does not correlate with other measures. Furthermore, the Dale Chall (DC) method also has a low-correlation with other methods. This highlights the possibility that these two measures may complement each other.

Fig. 3 Pearson (left) and Spearman (right) correlation coefficient heatmaps for RA measures

3.3 Experiment 3: Optimum RA measure to predict grade

The discovery of higher correlations with grades for DC and CL (experiment 1), and their low correlation with other methods (experiment 2), invites the possibility that combining the two could yield a higher correlation with grade. Their scores, R_{DC} and R_{CL} respectively, are combined for each report using linear weighted interpolation to produce our new measure R_{Ours} :

$$R_{Ours} = \alpha R_{DC} - (1 - \alpha) R_{CL}$$

R_{CL} is negated due to its negative correlation with grade as revealed in table 2. The interpolation weight, α , is empirically determined to maximise either the pearson and spearman correlation coefficient. $\alpha=0.8$ gives the highest value for spearman correlation coefficient (0.32) while $\alpha=0.2$ has the highest value for pearson correlation coefficient (0.15). These findings show some value in combining these two complementary measures to predict grade. This is likely due to relatively fewer overlapping features that they share (sentence counts) whereas other measures share more counts (notably word and letter). Finally, for completeness, our formula combining DC and CL using weight α is:

$$R_{ours} = \alpha \left(15.79 \frac{N_{dw}}{N_w} + 0.0496 \frac{N_{dw}}{N_s} \right) - (1 - \alpha) \left(5.88 \frac{N_l}{N_w} - 2.96 \frac{N_s}{N_w} - 15.8 \right)$$

Where counts N_{dw} , N_w , N_s , N_l are for difficult words, words, sentences and letters respectively.

4 DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY

Motivated to improve engineering students report writing communication skills through technology, and to assess the impact of remote learning, we found no difference between previous years for grades awarded and the classic readability measures for students who have experienced only remote learning and those who interacted face-to-face with peers at their beginning of study. This is not altogether unexpected – compared to skills that may require greater interaction with apparatus and other people, writing can be a skill mostly practiced alone with feedback provided asynchronously.

We found a limited use for these classic readability measures; most are highly correlated with each other and are only weakly correlated with grade. Given that the grade used in this study is an academic assessment that is not directly assessing readability, we believe the weak correlation is acceptable. Strikingly, two measures – Dale Chall and Coleman Liau - stand out with significantly stronger correlations. This suggests that these measures could be more useful to engineering educators than the more common go-to measures found in the literature: Flesch-Kincaid, Flesch Reading Ease and Automated Readability Index. In the case of multiple assessors, as is common in large faculties assessing capstone reports, these measures could be used to improve assessment reliability by including a machine-generate component into the mark scheme. However, their weak correlation suggests they are no replacement for human judgement.

Future work includes using our preferred readability measures to demonstrate progression through years of study. There is also potential to employ newer techniques of natural language processing with machine learning to devise an engineering education-specific automatic readability assessment measure which could support learning for specific engineering writing contexts. This would necessitate collecting a corpus with a sufficient number of samples to robustly train and evaluate any algorithms.

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